

Correlation of the Hammett Equation with the Solubility and Dissociation Constants of Benzoic Acid in Aquo-ethanolic Solutions

P. K. BISWAS and S. C. LAHIRI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 18 February 1993, accepted 29 July 1993

The correlation of solubility and the dissociation constants of benzoic acids with Hammett equation in aquo-ethanolic solutions has been attempted. The poor correlation of the solubilities with the Hammett equation arises from the difference in the factors responsible for solubilisation processes.

The dissociation constants in aquo-ethanolic mixtures can be well correlated with the Hammett equation and ρ is found to vary linearly with the percentage of the organic solvents. The deviations from linearity at 16, 34 and 64 wt% of ethanol can be correlated with the structural peculiarities of the solvent mixtures.

The Hammett equation¹⁻³ is widely used for correlation of equilibrium and kinetics of reactions of a class of chemical compounds of the same ligand family. Deviations of the solvent parameter, i.e. ρ -values are usually ascribed to changes in the reaction mechanism for the reaction and equilibrium paths. Variations of solvent naturally have important effects on the equilibrium and kinetics of reaction leading to a change in ρ -values reflecting the changes in solute-solvent interactions occurring in the system.

As part of our programme to study ion-solvent interactions, we have determined the dissociation constants and solubility of different substituted benzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures (0-100 wt% of ethanol) (Table 1). The correlation of solubility and the dissociation constants may therefore be examined in the light of Hammett equation which we present here.

Little attempt has been made to use Hammett equation to correlate the solubility values of benzoic acids. The phenomenon of solubility is an equilibrium process. We can write

$$\text{or } K_s = \frac{C_{\text{soln}} \times \gamma_{\text{soln}}}{a_{\text{solid}}} \approx C_{\text{soln(satd)}} \quad (2)$$

Since by convention a_{solid} is unity and γ_{soln} for neutral electrolytes can be taken to be unity, therefore, it is possible to write

$$\log \frac{C_{\text{soln(substituted acid)}}}{C_{\text{soln(benzoic acid)}}} = \rho_s \sigma \quad (3)$$

However, the relationship does not give the desired result. Little deviation may well arise from the possible error involved in assuming activity coefficients to be unity, particularly when the concentrations are high. But the effect must be small.

In spite of poor correlation it is seen that the factors responsible for dissolution are similar in case of *p*-Cl and *p*-Br acids but widely different in case of nitro-substituted acids probably due to strong dispersion effects. The effects due to substituent in the *ortho*-position will obviously be different due to proximity effect.

It is evident that the complicated interaction

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY AND pK VALUES OF BENZOIC ACID AND DIFFERENT SUBSTITUTED BENZOIC ACIDS IN EtOH + H₂O MIXTURES AT 298 K*

Wt% of EtOH	HBz		<i>o</i> -NHBz		<i>m</i> -NHBz		<i>p</i> -NHBz	
	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	pK _T						
0	0.028 4	4.20	0.047 1	2.30	0.020 4	3.53	0.002 5	3.45
8.0	0.038 9	4.36	0.057 3	2.61	0.027 1	3.74	0.003 1	3.54
16.4	0.057 7	4.55	0.061 6	2.82	0.045 3	3.82	0.005 0	3.71
25.3	0.120 1	4.85	0.182 2	3.21	0.124 1	4.17	0.007 4	3.81
34.4	0.359 3	5.03	0.326 3	3.56	0.542 2	4.35	0.008 5	3.98
44.0	0.778 5	5.38	0.933 2	3.92	1.279 9	4.70	0.009 1	4.23
54.1	1.306 1	5.63	1.488 7	4.24	1.613 2	4.96	0.010 0	4.35
64.7	1.731 6	6.05	2.008 7	4.64	1.910 9	5.26	0.011 0	4.46
76.0	2.203 4	6.20	2.382 0	5.08	2.319 8	5.78	0.022 6	4.79
87.6	2.665 6	6.46	2.524 2	4.41	2.479 7	5.34	0.034 5	4.86

Wt% of EtOH	<i>p</i> -ClHBz		<i>m</i> -ClHBz		<i>p</i> -NHBz	
	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	pK _T	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	pK _T	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	pK _T
0	0.000 5	3.92	0.002 6	3.87	0.000 3	3.98
8.0	0.001 0	4.04	0.003 7	3.98	0.000 4	4.18
16.4	0.001 4	4.33	0.005 5	4.21	0.000 7	4.36
25.3	0.002 7	4.50	0.015 6	4.42	0.001 3	4.58
34.4	0.007 3	4.78	0.064 9	4.71	0.003 6	4.71
44.0	0.018 5	4.95	0.147 3	4.86	0.009 5	4.92
54.1	0.039 0	5.27	0.328 6	5.22	0.020 7	5.28
64.7	0.065 8	5.49	0.439 8	5.44	0.036 3	5.60
76.0	0.106 1	5.71	0.499 5	5.69	0.060 0	5.82
87.6	0.151 2	5.88	0.509 1	5.75	0.088 3	6.10

*Solubility values accurate within 0.5 to 1.0%; pK values accurate within 0.02 to 0.03; HBz = benzoic acid, *o*-NHBz = *o*-nitrobenzoic acid, *m*-NHBz = *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-NHBz = *p*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-ClHBz = *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, *m*-ClHBz = *m*-chlorobenzoic acid, *p*-BrHBz = *p*-bromobenzoic acid.

phenomena affecting the solubility are different for various substituted acids and are not well-understood. The differences in solubilities of benzoic acids are due to the following factors. (a) Changes in dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions arising from the changes in dipole moments of solutes. (b) Changes in specific solvation like hydrogen-bonding interactions and association of molecules; association appears to be small in these solvents. (c) Changes in the dissociation of the molecules leading to changes in pH-values. The dissociation should increase with the increase in basicity of the mixed solvents but decrease due to decrease in dielectric constants. (d) Changes in the hydrophobic character of the solute due to substituents. (e) Changes in dispersion interactions,

which is particularly important when NO₂ groups are present.

For a solvent system, the variations in the nature of the solutes are particularly important. The variations may be partially reflected by the differences in the cohesive forces of the molecules (dependent on the crystal structure and bonding between adjacent molecules) which are related to the 'internal pressures' or solubility parameters (which express the cohesion between like molecules), given by⁵

$$\delta = P_i^{1/2} = \left(\frac{\Delta H_v - RT}{V} \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where ΔH_v is the heat of vapourisation of the molecule and V the molar volume of the

super-cooled liquid at the desired temperature. Thus, the factors affecting ΔH_v , temperature of the melting and boiling points of the solute are important.

The more alike the δ -values of the two components (solute and solvent) the greater is the mutual solubility. Thus, the differences in solubility parameters resulting from change in cohesive forces together with solute-solvent interactions, are responsible for the changed solubilities. The ratio of solubility of the substituted acid in water to that of benzoic acid may thus be roughly taken as an approximate measure of the solubility parameter of the substituted acid but the ratio will change in different solvents due to changed solute-solvent interactions.

As in case of aqueous solutions, the correlation of the dissociation constants of benzoic acids in ethanol + water mixtures has been made. It is known that the Hammett equation or the linear free energy relationship is based on the compensation of entropy and enthalpy changes on ionisation. For reactions of the type⁵,

the thermodynamic functions can be written in terms of internal (intrinsic to the molecule and ions of the acid and base) and external or environmental (resulting from the interaction of acid and base with the solvents) effects⁶⁻⁹,

$$\delta\Delta H^0 = \delta\Delta H_{\text{ext}}^0 + \delta\Delta H_{\text{int}}^0 \quad (6a)$$

$$\delta\Delta S^0 = \delta\Delta S_{\text{ext}}^0 + \delta\Delta S_{\text{int}}^0 \approx \delta\Delta S_{\text{ext}}^0 \quad (6b)$$

$\delta\Delta S_{\text{int}}^0$ is assumed to be zero for symmetrical reactions of the type (5) in a particular solvent system. The compensation of $\delta\Delta H_{\text{ext}}^0$ and $T\delta\Delta S_{\text{ext}}^0$ arising from the structural changes with addition of alcohol therefore leads to linear free energy relationship. The ρ -values at different percentages of mixed solvents obtained graphically (a) or average values from the relationship,

$$\rho = (\log \frac{K_{\text{sub}}}{K_0} / \sigma), \quad (b) \quad \text{are given as follows :}$$

wt % alcohol 0 (a, 1.0; b, 1.0), 8.0 (a, 1.09; b, 1.04), 16.4 (a, 0.97; b, 0.91), 25.3 (a, 1.24; b, 1.13), 34.4 (a, 1.10; b, 1.05), 44.0 (a, 1.47; b, 1.57), 54.1 (a, 1.49; b, 1.46), 64.7 (a, 1.87; b, 1.90), 76.0 (a, 1.77; b, 1.77), 87.6 (a, 1.89; b, 1.84), and 100% (a, 2.01) (extrapolated value). The values are in agreement with those reported by Sykes¹⁰ : $\rho_{50\% \text{ alc}} = 1.60$ and $\rho_{\text{ethanol}} = 1.96$. Curiously enough the plot of ρ -values against wt% of alcohol show excellent linearity passing through $\rho = 1$ at 0%. The deviations are observed at 16, 34 and 64 wt% of alcohol.

The changes in ρ -values with addition of alcohol may reflect the structural changes and the variation of solute-solvent interactions characterising the solvent mixtures.

Addition of alcohol enhances the structure formation of water which becomes maximum at $\sim X_2 = 0.1$ (about 20 wt%) beyond which structural collapse begins. The importance of solute-solvent interactions is manifested in the complex concentration dependence of excess thermodynamic properties of mixing ΔH^E (exothermic); $T\Delta S^E$ [negative maximum at $X_2 = 0.3$ (~50 wt%)] and ΔG^E [positive maximum of ΔG^E at $X_2 = 0.5 \approx (72 \text{ wt}\%)$].

It is to be noted that weakening of hydrophobic interactions ($0 \ll X_{\text{EtOH}} \ll 0.03$) occurs initially followed by strengthening of hydrophobic interactions upto $X_{\text{EtOH}} \approx 0.2$, beyond which hydrophobic interaction becomes weak. These may be the cause of deviations in ρ . But the ρ -values are very sensitive to the accuracy of K_T and slight error means a considerable change on ρ -values⁸. Moreover, the assumed constancy in σ -values with solvent composition may have some effect.

It is to be noted that the substituent effects are dependent on three different modes of interactions of which inductive and resonance effects

can be assumed to remain unchanged with solvent composition but the field effects (electronic effect) must be dependent on the solvents^{3,9}. This is due to change in the (i) distance of the substituents from the reaction centre, (ii) effective dielectric constant of the medium and (iii) solute-solvent interactions.

The prediction for the change in substituent constants have been made by Dewar and Grisdale¹³,

$$\sigma = F/r_{ij} - M\pi_{ij} \quad (7)$$

where F and M are constants determining the field and resonance effect and π_{ij} and r_{ij} are the atom-atom polarisability of the aromatic system and the distance between the points of attachment to the aromatic system of the substituent and side-chain. The change in σ with solvents is thus expected^{7,14} and the method of evaluation of σ by other methods should be explored.

The ρ -value is found to increase with increase in alcohol concentration. The positive values of ρ indicate that electron-withdrawing group increases the equilibrium constant for reaction (5) by stabilising the negative charge developed in the product^{4,6}. From equation (5), we have

$$\rho \sigma = \log K = -\log \frac{[\text{HBz}]_{\text{sub}}}{[\text{HBz}]} + \log \frac{[\text{Bz}^-]_{\text{subs}}}{[\text{Bz}^-]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or } \rho = -\rho_s + \rho_1 \quad (9)$$

The value of ρ depends on the combined effects of the relative stabilities and equilibrium concentrations of Bz^- (subs) compared to Bz^- , and HBz (subs) compared to HBz .

It has been found that the solubilities of HBz (subs) are decreased enormously with electron-withdrawing substituent making ρ_s to be negative or $-\rho_s$ to be positive but (Bz^-) (subs) is more stabilised than $[\text{Bz}^-]$ which means ρ_1 to be positive. The effective stabilisation of $[\text{HBz}]$ compared to $[\text{HBz}]_{\text{subs}}$ arises from the change in dipole-dipole, diole-quadrupole and dis-

persion forces. But the anion stabilisation is governed mainly by hydrogen bonding and electrostatic effects. ρ_s value, though cannot be calculated accurately, has been found to be negative as predicted but ρ_1 cannot be calculated.

But it is apparent from equation (7) that σ -value should differ in case of anions compared to neutral molecules as the field and mesomeric effects are likely to be different.

Moreover, the increased dissociation of the nitro or chloro substituted benzoic acids obviously means an increased stabilisation of anions compared to Bz^- . However, due to solubility limitations, the concentration of Bz^- (subs) is less than the concentration of Bz^- ion. Thus ρ_1 is negative and varies in such a way to make ρ positive and equal to 1 in water. In aquo-alcoholic mixtures the variations of ρ_s and ρ_1 follow the similar pattern as in water.

It is apparent that ρ or σ values can in no way be correlated with the structural properties of solutes in solution. But correlation of ρ -values with thermodynamic parameters is possible and it is desirable to find out whether σ -values are really independent of solvent.

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